

STRATEGY OF THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION, INFORMATICS, COPYRIGHT AND STATISTICS OF CENTRAL KALTENG PROVINCE IN DEVELOPING THE INFORMATION COMMUNITY (KIM)

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Abstract

This study examines the efforts of the Office of Communication, Informatics, Encryption, and Statistics of Central Kalimantan Province in fostering and strengthening Community Information Groups (Kelompok Informasi Masyarakat/KIM) as community-based public communication partners. Using a qualitative approach with a descriptive method, supported by in-depth interviews with key informants namely a Senior Public Relations Officer of the Office of Communication, Informatics, Encryption, and Statistics of Central Kalimantan Province and a KIM activist in Central Kalimantan, the Chairperson of KIM Bintang Jaya Itah this research explores how the provincial government carries out capacity building, institutional development, and improvements in digital infrastructure to enhance KIM performance in disseminating public information. The findings show that government support is manifested through structured training in public communication, digital literacy, and citizen journalism; continuous mentoring in the use of platforms such as kim.id and KIM Digital; and the implementation of tiered coordination involving KIM networks at the provincial, district, sub-district, and village levels. Diskominfosantik has institutional duties and functions in the fields of public communication, informatics, and information dissemination. KIM is one of the strategic programs that serves as an instrument for community-based information empowerment, making this topic relevant to the role of government institutions. Studies related to KIM in Central Kalimantan are still relatively limited; therefore, this research provides a new contribution in the context of developing community information institutions at the regional level. Although various initiatives have been implemented, several challenges remain, such as limited community management capacity among KIM implementers, uneven digital skills, and a relatively high dependence on government facilitation to support operational activities. This study shows that effective collaboration and role-sharing in producing content relevant to local needs are essential. The Office of Communication, Informatics, Encryption, and Statistics of Central Kalimantan Province acts not only as a regulator but also as a facilitator, mentor, and community empowerer in the field of information. Overall, this study concludes that government efforts through the Office of Communication, Informatics, Encryption, and Statistics of Central Kalimantan Province in the development of Community Information Groups (KIM) fall into the effective category and encourage KIM to be more active in producing and disseminating information. In the era of hoaxes and disinformation, the government requires trustworthy community-based information channels, and KIM represents one such solution; however, there are still KIMs that remain inactive in certain regions or districts and therefore require further attention and guidance.

Keywords: Communication Methods, Radicalism Prevention, Students

INTRODUCTION

The development of information technology in Indonesia encourages local governments to build public communication patterns that are more open, fast, and easily accessible to citizens in various regions. In Central Kalimantan Province, the need for a regular flow of information arises along with the vast geographical conditions, diverse community characteristics, and scattered distribution of settlements. These challenges prompted the provincial government to develop various communication strategies so that the community, including those far from the center of government, remains informed about regional development. This KIM acts as an intermediary between the government and the community, bridging the communication and knowledge gap. This is a previous study but there is a difference entitled communication strategies used in socializing the Community Information

Community (KIM) program. To facilitate the analysis of communication strategies, this study uses the five-stage communication planning process of Cangara Martin & Maulida, (2022), which includes research, activity planning, implementation, evaluation (measurement), and the final action is reporting. Meanwhile, the author uses a different theory. The diffusion of innovation theory developed by Everett M. Rogers describes how a new idea, practice, or object is spread to members of a social system through a communication process that takes place over a certain period. Rogers also formulated four stages in the diffusion process: knowledge, persuasion, decision, and confirmation. In the initial stage, individuals begin to recognize the innovation and understand its function. In this context, the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communications, Informatics, Cryptography, and Statistics Agency (Diskominfosantik) is implementing various public communication programs, ranging from content production and digital information channels, strengthening communications infrastructure, and fostering community groups. This strategy illustrates how government communications are not solely focused on delivering messages but also on creating a more organized and multi-layered communications ecosystem. The Communications and Information Technology Office (Diskominfosantik) Strategic Plan for 2021–2026 demonstrates a strong push to expand public access to development information. The provincial government continues to increase the volume of published content, strengthen collaboration with various media outlets, and develop official information channels such as the Public Information and Communications Agency (PPID) portal and satellite-based broadcasting services. The provision of fiber optic networks and the increase in the number of signaled villages over the years demonstrate that public communication is being built on a gradually expanding technological foundation. In this process, the government is not relying solely on formal media but is also encouraging the emergence of community-based information networks to bring messages closer to citizens' lives. These steps demonstrate an awareness that information delivery cannot be effective if it relies solely on government communication channels.

The Community Information Community (KIM) exists as a communication tool formed and managed by citizens to manage information independently. The KIM concept enables communities not only to receive information but also to participate in the production, processing, and dissemination of information related to local needs. KIM has developed in various regions in Indonesia, including Central Kalimantan, and has become a tool that helps citizens understand development programs, government policies, and social activities. KIM operates through collaborative work principles that strengthen two-way communication between the government and the community. With the expansion of the KIM network at the village, sub-district, and district levels, the community information space has become more diverse because residents have access to information produced by the community itself. In the context of Central Kalimantan, the development of the KIM is structured based on regulatory frameworks, including regulations issued by the Ministry of Communication and Informatics. The KIM formation process is conducted through community consultations, followed by registration and guidance by the district/city Communication and Informatics Offices, and finally established through a regional government decree. These stages demonstrate that the KIM's existence is not merely an administrative program, but the result of community dialogue and participation. This formation pattern creates a hierarchical communication channel from the provincial government to grassroots communities. This systematic flow allows for a more targeted flow of public information, while also providing space for the KIM to contribute to the dissemination of relevant local information.

To ensure the optimal functioning of the KIM network, the Central Kalimantan Communications and Information Technology Office (Diskominfosantik) provides various forms of support, including training in public communication, information literacy, news writing, and digital content production. This capacity building aims to equip KIM members with skills that enable them to manage information creatively and responsibly. Furthermore, the provincial government has introduced digital platforms such as kim.id and KIM Digital to support faster and more standardized content distribution. Technical assistance is provided on an ongoing basis to ensure KIM members understand the use of these digital tools. This strengthening provides opportunities for KIM to produce more varied local content that can be accessed by the wider public through online information channels. In Central Kalimantan, 153 KIMs have been formed in the Regency/City, namely Palangka Raya City 12 KIMs, East Barito Regency 90 KIMs, Sukamara Regency 12 KIMs, Babelo Regency 13 KIMs, Pulang Pisau Regency 2 KIMs, Katingan Regency 6 KIMs, Kapuas Regency 3 KIMs, East Kotawaringin Regency 3 KIMs, West Kotawaringin Regency 6 KIMs, Gunung Mas Regency 1 KIM, Seruyan Regency 1 KIM, Lamandau Regency 2 KIMs, Murung Raya Regency 2 KIMs. There is one Regency that has not yet formed a KIM, namely a Regency that has not yet formed a KIM and is registered on KIM.id. Data source: KIM.id in 2025. This study aims to describe how the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government, through the Communication, Informatics, Cryptography, and Statistics Office, builds and strengthens the Community Information Community (KIM) as a citizen-based public

communication network. In the era of hoaxes and disinformation, the government needs a trusted community-based information channel — KIM is one solution. This study seeks to explain the forms of government intervention ranging from providing access to digital information, improving communication literacy, technical training, mentoring the kim.id and KIM Digital platforms, to institutional development aimed at creating a more orderly flow of information that can reach areas with diverse geographical characteristics. The urgency of this research lies in the need to understand how strengthening KIM can address the challenges of public communication in a large and heterogeneous region such as Central Kalimantan, especially so that the community, including those in remote areas, continues to receive consistent development information and can play an active role in the production and distribution of local information.

METHOD

This study applies a qualitative approach, with descriptive methods supported by in-depth interviews through informants, namely the Middle Expert Public Relations Officer of the Communication, Informatics, Cryptography and Statistics Office of Central Kalimantan Province and the Head of KIM Bintang Jaya Itah, this study explores how the provincial government carries out capacity building, institutional development, and digital infrastructure improvements to encourage KIM performance in disseminating public information. in-depth interviews with the Communication Office and one of the KIM Activists in Central Kalimantan as well as brief observations of daily work activities within the agency. Interviews were conducted in a structured manner using question guidelines designed to trace the policy flow, information delivery patterns, and communication strategies implemented. Observations were used to directly see the dynamics of interactions and coordination flows between sections so that the collected data came not only from informant narratives, but also from field observations. The selection of informants was carried out purposively, while data from interviews and observations were recorded, transcribed, and then analyzed through a process of reduction, thematic grouping, and interpretation to produce a coherent description of official communication practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Everett M. Rogers' Theory of Diffusion of Innovation

The 1944 article "The People's Choice," written by Paul Lazarsfeld, Bernard Berelson, and H. Gaudet, laid the foundation for the development of the theory of diffusion of innovation. This theory explains that messages received by communicators from mass media have a significant influence on others. In other words, when an innovation is introduced and disseminated through mass media, the urge to encourage people to follow or adopt it becomes stronger. In its early development, this theory positioned opinion leaders as figures who played a role in shaping public attitudes and actions. Mass media was seen as having a significant influence in disseminating new discoveries or ideas, especially when the information was conveyed by trusted public figures. However, the spread of innovations can also reach audiences directly without intermediaries. Rogers and Shoemaker (1971) stated that diffusion is a process by which an invention is distributed to members of a social system. The theory of diffusion of innovation, developed by Everett M. Rogers, describes how a new idea, practice, or object is spread to members of a social system through a communication process that takes place over a period of time. Within this framework, an innovation is considered new when an individual or group has no prior experience using or evaluating it. The spread of new ideas occurs through formal and informal channels, allowing potential adopters to receive, understand, and consider the information. Rogers explained that diffusion is not simply the transmission of a message, but a series of social interactions that influence how individuals develop attitudes toward an innovation.

Rogers also formulated four stages in the diffusion process: knowledge, persuasion, decision, and confirmation. In the initial stage, individuals begin to recognize the innovation and understand its function. The next stage involves forming an attitude that supports or rejects the new idea. Afterward, individuals determine whether to adopt or reject it, followed by a process of strengthening the decision through personal experience or feedback from the social environment. Furthermore, Rogers divided adopter groups into five categories: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and the slowest to accept change. This division demonstrates that the spread of innovation moves gradually and is influenced by social characteristics and the readiness of each individual. The theory of innovation diffusion is relevant to research on the development of Community Information Communities (KIM) in Central Kalimantan because it helps explain how new programs, digital platforms, and communication practices are introduced and accepted by KIM activists down to the village level. The strategies of the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communication, Informatics, Cryptography, and Statistics Office, such as public communication training, mentoring in the use of kim.id and KIM Digital,

increasing information literacy, and tiered coaching, can be understood as a series of innovation dissemination processes that align with the stages of knowledge, persuasion, decision, and confirmation in Rogers' framework. KIM itself functions as an interpersonal channel that accelerates the adoption of public communication innovations because its members act as a group that is more ready to accept and disseminate new ideas through direct contact with the community. Thus, the theory of diffusion of innovation provides a foundation for observing how the government expands the flow of public information, how KIM members adopt new practices in the production and distribution of information, and how the citizen-based communication network gradually develops according to social dynamics in various regions of Central Kalimantan.

Central Kalimantan Communications and Information Technology Office & Central Kalimantan Public Information Community (KIM)

The state of communication in Central Kalimantan, as depicted in the 2021-2026 Strategic Plan of the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communications, Informatics, Cryptography, and Statistics Office, shows that the provincial government continues to develop various information delivery mechanisms so that people throughout the region, including those far from the center of government, can receive development updates more quickly and broadly. This strategy is implemented through a combination of content dissemination, strengthening public information systems, improving digital communication infrastructure, and empowering communities as part of the regional information network. This multi-layered approach demonstrates how public communication is designed to reach various segments of society, through mass media, official government online channels, expanded connectivity networks, and fostering local information groups that serve as intermediaries for information flow within their regions. In this way, information delivery in Central Kalimantan does not rely solely on a single channel but is built through a series of complementary programs that are strengthened year after year. The communications landscape in Central Kalimantan, as outlined in the Strategic Plan, demonstrates that the regional government is striving to expand public access to development information through various digital and conventional communication programs. The flow of information is strengthened by increasing the amount of content disseminated to print, online, and electronic media. The content volume increased from 500 in 2021 and continues to increase until it reaches the target of 725 in 2026.

This increase demonstrates a strategy of making information more easily accessible to the public online. At the same time, the provincial government continues to implement public information transparency with consistent budgeting, for example, by allocating more than IDR 243 million in 2021, which will then increase to IDR 295 million in 2025 to ensure the continuity of open and publicly monitored information access services. This combination of content dissemination and strengthening official information channels allows the public to have more access points when seeking to understand the direction of regional policies and development activities. The availability of digital communications infrastructure is another foundation that is being gradually expanded. The percentage of villages with signal coverage increased from 67% in 2020 to 98% in 2026, indicating that previously difficult-to-reach areas are gradually becoming connected through modern communications services. This is reinforced by the construction of the provincial government's fiber optic network, which increased from 33 locations in 2021 to 43 locations in 2026. This network enables faster access to policies, public services, and development information for the public and regional officials. So that data integration and communication processes between work units become smoother and connected to available public channels.

The strategy to strengthen community communication is also implemented through digital literacy activities and the development of community information groups (KIM). The digital literacy program, facilitated by the local government, is designed to broaden citizens' understanding of the use of communication technology. Participants increased from 300 in 2021 to 700 in 2025, indicating a push to create a community that is better equipped to utilize everyday digital information. KIM is being developed as an additional channel that helps residents at the sub-district level share development information, with coverage continuing to grow to nearly 98% by 2026. These initiatives ensure that information distribution relies not only on official government channels but also on community networks strengthened through mentoring in regional communication programs. The Community Information Community (KIM) exists as a forum formed directly by citizens to manage and disseminate information independently, creatively, and sustainably. This concept makes citizens not only recipients of information, but also managers and drivers of the flow of information within their communities. The communication paradigm adopted is no longer one-way, but rather "communication with people," so that the process of information sharing occurs through dialogue and collaboration between citizens and various parties. KIM has now grown extensively with 3,594 groups, involving 7,567 members, spread across 31 provinces, 259

regencies/cities, 1,022 sub-districts, and 3,310 villages/wards. The existence of this extensive network makes KIM function as a community that is continuously connected, reliable, and able to act in an integrated manner to support the community in obtaining accurate and easily accessible information. In practice, KIMs in various regions serve as communication bridges between the government and the public through activities that expand the flow of public information. KIMs help bridge development issues, government programs, citizen needs, and various forms of local aspirations that need to be conveyed through appropriate channels. KIMs also encourage the development of intelligent and participatory communities because citizens are directly involved in collecting, processing, and disseminating information. The partnership between the government and KIMs is regulated by Minister of Communication and Information Regulation No. 8 of 2019, which mandates regional communication agencies to collaborate with these communities as stakeholders. Based on this foundation, KIMs have room to develop more actively, particularly in facilitating two-way communication processes that are more responsive to citizen needs.

The development and empowerment of KIM is carried out through various programs designed to strengthen the capacity and quality of its information activities. These activities include providing information materials such as articles, infographics, educational videos, and guides that KIM members can directly use in their communication activities in their respective regions. Furthermore, technical and non-technical training, ranging from technical guidance and workshops to literacy programs, provides opportunities for KIM members to improve their information management and publication skills. The government also holds competitions and awards for active and impactful KIMs, thus encouraging continued innovation. Furthermore, mapping activities are conducted regularly to update officially registered KIM data, allowing the public to access the latest information on KIM locations, members, and categories throughout Indonesia.

Through this series of programs, KIM is developing as a community that not only disseminates information but also encourages more advanced and productive community communication dynamics. Although the Community Information Group (KIM) was designed as a strategic partner for the government in disseminating information and improving community literacy, in reality, KIM's presence in Central Kalimantan is still not optimal. Ideally, KIM is expected to be an active, sustainable information agent integrated with the regional digital transformation agenda. However, the actual situation shows that most KIMs remain passive, their coaching is not sustainable, and their institutional support and human resource capacity are still limited. Furthermore, KIMs' use of digital technology is suboptimal, and community participation in supporting KIM's functions is relatively low. This gap between ideal and actual conditions creates a research gap, necessitating a more in-depth study of the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communications and Information Technology Office's strategy for developing KIMs, as well as the effectiveness of the approaches taken in strengthening KIM's role in the region.

Public Information Flow Management Patterns through the KIM Network in Central Kalimantan

The management of public information flows in Central Kalimantan through the KIM network is built on a clear regulatory foundation, which serves as a reference for driving government and public communication activities. Informants stated that the initial basis for KIM development refers to "Minister of Communication and Informatics Regulation Number 4 of 2024." This regulation helps the Communication and Informatics Agency formulate communication policy directions and guides integrated information delivery patterns from the provincial to district/city to village levels. This demonstrates that communication channels are not built sporadically, but through a structured framework to ensure easier public access to public information. Understanding this regulatory framework serves as the foundation for the KIM network in strengthening inter-regional message flows. In practice, the flow of public information flows through the KIM structure, which is gradually established at the village, sub-district, district, and regency/city levels. Informants explained that its formation is carried out through a "community deliberation" which then continues with a registration and coaching process by the regency/city Communications and Information Office before finally being established through a regional government decree. This process demonstrates that the community communication network does not emerge from unilateral instructions, but rather from internal community dialogue that is then strengthened by government institutional development. Through this pattern, each region has a aligned information distribution channel, from the provincial government down to smaller community levels. To ensure the smooth flow of information, the Kominfosantik Office implements a multi-layered coordination pattern involving responsible persons at the provincial and regency/city levels. Informants mentioned that the office appoints "PICs/persons in charge at the Provincial Communications and Information Office and the Regency/City Communications and Information Office" to ensure each region has a verified KIM list. The existence of these PICs enables routine two-way communication, both in the delivery of information and in monitoring KIM activities. This layered coordination pattern provides a

workflow that allows the government to know field conditions in real-time, including publication developments and problems faced by each KIM in the region. The Communications and Informatics Agency (Kominfosantik) not only distributes information but also builds the capacity of KIM (Information and Communications Institutions) to process, produce, and disseminate informative content. Informants explained that various training courses are provided, such as "public communication training, information literacy, and writing local news and content," designed to help KIM members convey messages clearly and compellingly. Assistance in the use of digital platforms is also part of the strategy to strengthen the flow of information, for example through the use of kim.id and KIM Digital. Through these activities, the flow of information is not only one-way from the government, but is also enriched with the production of local content by KIM members who understand the context of their communities. The pattern of public information dissemination runs through a hierarchical flow from the provincial Communications and Informatics Agency to the district/city, then continues to the sub-district and village KIMs. Informants stated that "government information is distributed through the Communications and Information Office (Diskominfo) → KIM district/city → KIM sub-district/village" as a message flow model that ensures information reaches the grassroots level. In addition to relying on administrative structures, KIM also builds relationships with various parties such as village governments, schools, MSMEs, PKK, and community leaders. The involvement of many parties makes the message dissemination channel wider, especially when the community needs fast information regarding public services, government activities, and local issues.

Monitoring information quality is also part of the public information flow management model. An informant stated that the Communication, Informatics, and Information Technology Agency "constantly monitors and supervises news published by KIM," although this monitoring is still done manually because account access is held by district/city offices. Nevertheless, this strategy helps maintain accurate message flow and aligns with government publication standards. This monitoring also serves as a basis for evaluating KIM's productivity and identifying areas requiring further assistance. Strengthening information quality supports the creation of a more consistent and credible message flow for the public. Although the information dissemination structure is in place, challenges remain, particularly regarding KIM activists' understanding of community management. An informant stated that many KIM members "don't understand what community building is all about" and tend to rely on government support or funding. To address this situation, the agency provides technical guidance and various training programs to encourage KIM members to be more independent in managing their information dissemination activities. Furthermore, an appreciation program for active KIM members is also provided as a form of motivation to maintain the sustainability of public communication. Through a combination of training, mentoring, and community empowerment, the flow of public information in Central Kalimantan is increasingly developing as a communication network that is responsive to community needs.

So, simply put, the Strategy of the Communication, Informatics, Cryptography and Statistics Service of Central Kalimantan Province in Developing the Public Information Community (KIM) is as follows:

KIM Communication Capacity Strengthening Strategy and Response to Field Challenges

The strategy to strengthen the communication capacity of KIM in Central Kalimantan begins with improving the basic competencies of KIM members so they can carry out public communication activities in a more targeted manner. An informant from the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communications and Informatics Agency, Public Relations Officer Young Expert Ferawati, S.Sos., M.Med. Kom, stated that the Communications and Informatics Agency provides “public communication and information literacy training” designed to enable KIM members to develop clear and easily understood messages. The training provides provisions on how to package information effectively, whether in written, visual, or digital content that suits the needs of each region. This step demonstrates that capacity building is not only focused on technical aspects, but also on how to build communication channels that are acceptable to the wider community.

A further strategy is evident in mentoring the use of digital platforms as the primary means of disseminating information. Informants explained that KIM members are guided in utilizing platforms such as kim.id and the KIM Digital facility provided by the central government through KOMDIGI. This mentoring helps KIM members understand how to use the website, upload content, and utilize online publication features that facilitate the dissemination process. This strengthening of digital competencies allows the flow of public information to move more quickly and reach people accustomed to accessing information through digital devices. In addition to basic training and digital platform usage, improving content production skills is also part of the strengthening strategy. Informants described "training in writing local news and information content," which includes citizen journalism techniques such as the 5W+1H, creating short video content, and photographing local products. This training helps KIM convey local issues more engagingly, so that the content serves not only as a

means of conveying information but also as a means of educating the public. The ability to produce creative content is KIM's strength in presenting information that is relevant to the daily lives of people in villages and sub-districts. Capacity building is also carried out through institutional development to ensure a more streamlined KIM structure in various regions. Itah Raden Roro Endah, a KIM activist in Central Kalimantan and the Chairperson of KIM Bintang Jaya, stated that this training helps KIM "be structured, understand its duties, and function as a government partner." Institutional development includes understanding organizational structure, division of tasks, and how to manage community activities. This step helps KIM maintain consistent communication activities and strengthens internal capabilities in managing information and coordinating with local governments. The implementation of this strengthening strategy still faces several challenges in the field, particularly in terms of KIM activists' understanding of how to build a community. Informants stated that "many KIM activists still don't understand how to build a community" and tend to rely on government assistance for facilities and funding. This situation indicates that some KIM members are still at an early stage in understanding the essence of the information community as a movement based on community participation.

Dependence on government support is one factor that needs to be addressed through a more sustainable empowerment and mentoring approach. The Communication, Informatics, and Information Technology Agency (Kominfosantik) responded to this challenge by expanding the scope of technical guidance and advanced training. Informants stated that the agency continues to strive to provide "technical guidance and training that is beneficial for KIM" to spark the creativity and activity of KIM activists in the field. The training serves as a forum for sharing experiences between regions, while also helping KIM observe how other communities carry out their communication tasks. This approach creates a collective learning space that can increase KIM members' motivation and strengthen their ability to overcome obstacles in their respective areas. As part of its sustainability strategy, the agency also provides awards and non-material incentives to active and productive KIMs. The informant explained that the Kominfosantik Agency is "committed to providing appreciation for active KIMs" and is preparing an innovation plan in the form of an Inspirational KIM Figure award for 2026. This appreciation program encourages KIM members to continue working and strengthen their contribution to disseminating public information. In addition to motivating individuals, the award serves as a symbol of moral support from the government for communities that consistently strive to disseminate positive and educational information within the community.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government through the Communication, Informatics, Cryptography and Statistics Agency involves KIM as part of the community information network. Strengthening digital access, increasing the number of published content, developing communication infrastructure, and providing platforms such as kim.id and KIM Digital are the foundations that support the flow of information to reach various regions. KIM management is carried out through a tiered formation process, institutional development, and layered coordination between provincial and district/city agencies. Based on the results of the interview, the Central Kalimantan Provincial Communication, Informatics, Cryptography and Statistics Agency's Strategy in Developing the Community Information Community (KIM) is in the category of quite effective and encourages KIM to be more active in producing and disseminating information in the midst of the era of hoaxes and disinformation, the government needs a trusted community-based information channel, KIM is one solution. This includes in the context of local issues close to people's lives. Despite this, several challenges remain, particularly related to the capacity of KIM members to understand independent community management. Dependence on government facilities and limitations in content production are barriers that need to be addressed through continued mentoring. The provincial government has attempted to address these challenges through training, technical guidance, practice-sharing forums, and appreciation programs to enable KIM's continued growth. With these steps, KIM has the potential to become a stronger, more adaptive, and more responsive public communication channel to the needs of communities in various regions of Central Kalimantan. There are also still inactive KIMs in the regions or regencies that require attention and guidance.

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